
CORRUPTION AND DEEPENING CRISES OF DEVELOPMENT: NIGERIA'S POLITICAL LEADERSHIP IN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This paper examined corruption and deepening crises of development in Nigeria. Noting that development is a double-edged affair, which must transcend all nook and cranny of the Nigerian state. For the development Nigeria yawns for to materialize, corruption and corrupt practices must firstly be curtailed in the circle of political leaders. Hence political intrigues as cover for corruption among political elites will continue to occasion and account for ineffective political leadership with its grave -impact which can never be over-emphasized. The paper made use of secondary sources of data, historical descriptive analysis and the Modernization theory of development as its framework of analysis to argue that of all the deepening crises militating against Nigeria's quest for socio-political and economic development, the most daunting appear to be untamable corruption. The multi-dimensional consequences of corrupt practices on a nation's socio-political and economic development cannot be overemphasized, as virtually all sectors of the country, including education, health, agriculture, politics, technology, etc., are negatively affected, with the resultant outcome like extreme poverty, high level of illiteracy, economic dependency, technological backwardness, political instability, etc. The central opinion of this paper is that corruption has been completely institutionalized into the contemporary Nigerian economic and socio-political systems and this is now reflecting in the growth and development of the nation. It was discovered that all forms of corruption manifested in bribery, frauds, embezzlement, election rigging, examination malpractice etc. are noticeable in Nigeria. The conclusion however, is that no matter the magnitude of natural resources present, the size of the foreign exchange earnings, technological know-how, the efficiency of labour and the availability of basic infrastructure, development cannot be sustained in Nigeria except corruption is eradicated.

Keywords: Corruption, Development, Underdevelopment, Crises of Development, Political Leadership.

Introduction

Corruption in Nigeria is a phenomenon which increases in quantity, intensity and in a geometric formation. Corruption has a diver stating consequence on both the economy and the citizens. Corruption constitutes a huge problem to the standard of living of citizens. In the Nigeria society, corruption has rendered millions of Nigerians uneducated, reduced the standard of living, and increased the cost of living (Aluko, 2019). This is due to mismanagement, embezzlement, misappropriation of public funds. Nigeria has been consistent in among the 10th most corrupt nations of 10 year report of Transparency International for ten years. Due to the corrupt nature of the Nigeria state, some international business men find it difficult to establish their business in Nigeria.

Despite the abundance of natural mineral resources (solid and liquid), Nigeria is ranked among the 25th poorest countries in the world, corruption retards the growth of the economy and development (Page, 2017). Corruption encourages political instability, impedes economic growth, encourages social unrest, and crime infested environment. It breeds inefficiency, incompetence, mediocrity, unethical values and other base instincts in man such as greed, avarice, and rapacity.

Leadership style in Nigeria can be classified as imposition. This is because; the manner at which leaders emerge in Nigeria is being characterized by widespread of electoral malpractices, such as rigging, thuggery, snatching of ballot boxes, intimidation of voters, etc. This has made the choices of the electorates to be defeated because those they voted for do not emerge the winners. This has led to a poor representation and bad leadership thereby causing share impediments in the nation building. Once there is bad leadership, there is a tendency that the policies the leader will be making will not be that of the populace but for that of the personal aggrandizement of those that made them seize the power (Ogbeidi, 2012).

The effect of corruption and poor leadership is being felt in all the aspects of the Nigerian polity. The variables have led to a poor infrastructural facilities, poor representation, poor health care facilities, decay in the economy, and constant devaluation of the Nigeria currency. Nigeria's socio-politico-economic history has revealed that many of its leaders over the years have been using the iron law of oligarchy which states that:

All forms of organizations, regardless of how democratic they may be at the start will eventually and inevitably develop oligarchic tendencies, thus making true democracy practically and theoretically impossible especially in large groups and complex organizations (Obokoh, 2020).

The iron law of oligarchy explains in the Nigeria context, the triumph of the leaders' ambitions for office over the membership's revolutionary goals. Many of the leaders have tended to plunder, defraud, embezzle, mismanage and in the process envy one another with impunity and relish (Bamidele 2019). He went further to state that the leaders have also been possessive, egoistic, selfish, individualistic, callous, greedy and secretive. The leaders and their regimes/administrations/governments were deeply engrossed in excessive acts of corruption, impropriety, mismanagement and squanderism.

Statement of the Problem

The reverberation effects of the failure of leadership, corruption and bad governance are being felt across all sectors and segment of Nigeria. Unemployment, insecurity, crude oil

thefts, dearth of infrastructures, education, health services, transportation, accommodation, communication, medication and etc. Nigeria has remained a laggard in social, political and economic developments. Nigeria's socio-political-economic history has revealed that many of its leaders over the years have been using the "iron law of oligarchy" which explains the triumph of the leaders' ambitions for office over the membership's revolutionary goals.

Many of the leaders have tended to plunder, defraud, embezzle, corrupt, mismanage and in the process envy one another with impunity and relish. They have also been possessive, egoistic, selfish, individualistic, callous, greedy and secretive. The leaders and their regimes/administrations/governments were deeply engrossed in excessive acts of corruption, impropriety, mismanagement and squander mania. In addition, all available means were employed by Nigerian political leaders to 'grab' power including the blatant rigging of elections, manipulation of census figures, violence, thuggery, arson, vandalism, gangsterism, corruption, religious bigotry, regionalism, tribalism, ethnic sentiments and acts of brigandage.

Consequently, neglect of public interest, malpractices of all forms, crimes of every description, mendacity, lack of candour, readiness to cheat, grabbing, philistinism, egotism, ethnic and sectional inclinations have been the order of the day for many years. These have precipitated violence, national disintegration, abject poverty and socio-political-economic instability (Olayiwola, 2016). Hence the devastating problems of the failure of leadership and the enigmatic nature of corruption and bad governance which have stalled Nigeria's quest for socio-politico economic development over the years prompted the review.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this review is to examine corruption and deepening crises of development: Nigerians political leadership in perspective. The specific objectives are to:

- a) Assess leadership and governance in Nigeria
- b) Assess the political intrigues as a cover for ineffective political leadership and corruption in Nigeria
- c) Discuss the impact of leadership crisis and corrupt acts on national development in Nigeria

Methodology

The methodology employed in this review includes analysis based on data collected from academic journals, books, Nigerian Newspapers, magazines, internet-based documentations and observation. Other sources include reports of Transparency International, the UNDP, NEEDS and MDGs materials.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual Framework

Corruption

The most simplified and popular definition adopted by the World Bank (2014) on corruption is 'the abuse of public power for private benefit'. Corruption can be defined as anti-social behaviour conferring improper benefits contrary to legal and moral norms, which undermines the authorities' capacity to secure the welfare of all citizens (Aluko, 2009). Corruption is the perversion of integrity or state of affairs through bribery, favour or moral depravity. Corruption is a conscious and well planned act by a person or group of persons to appropriate by unlawful means the wealth of another person (Dawood, 2019).

Corruption is any decision, act or conduct that subverts the integrity of people in authority or institutions charged with promoting, defending or sustaining the democratization process, thereby undermining its effectiveness in performing its assigned roles (Dawood, 2019). Political corruption can be defined as “a method of exploitation by which a constituent part of the public sphere is exploited as if it were part of the market sphere (Mudasiru, 2015). Political corruption is located within the institutions of government legislatures, courts, bureaucracies and statutory bodies such as parastatals, corporations or commissions. It is constituted by transactions or exchanges of public resources and benefits between actors, some or all of whom are officials or public representatives (Mudasiru, 2015).

The concepts of Corruption, Leadership and Development have attained important usage in the lexicon of third world countries of the world – situated mainly in Africa, Asia and Latin America. They have become important concepts that tend to explain how some countries of the world, through constituted authorities, are utilizing the resources at their disposal to attain their desired societal ends and bolster the capacity of citizens, while also attempting to overcome structural obstacles to such desirable ends. Nigeria with its vast endowment of human and material resources features prominently in this list. Following the attainment of political independence in October 1960, the country exuded bright prospects of development potentials that could lead Africa, nay the newly decolonized nations, on the path of socio-economic and material wellbeing of the citizenry.

Development

The concept of development refers to the changes and progress in a country's political system over time. Political development involves changes in government structure, political processes and people's participation in politics. It is important to throw some light on the concept “development” in order to really understand the phenomenon of underdevelopment in Nigeria. Development as a concept has been defined in various ways by scholars from different schools of thought and various social science disciplines. It has ranged from a narrow perspective in terms of a rise in per capita income to broader perspectives which include high performance in human and social development index in a given country. For instance, Jair and Quintella (2018) conceptualized authentic development as based on self-reliance where people's creative energy and labour are released in the attempt to emancipate the entire population from all natural and man-made obstacles. Development has also been conceptualized as a process that leads to increased capacity of a people to have control over material assets, intellectual resources and ideology, as well as the ability to obtain physical necessities of life, participation in government, political and economic independence, adequate education, gender equality, sustainable development and peace. Nowadays, Development is seen in more concrete and qualitative terms as an ongoing democratic and liberating process that ensures the satisfaction of basic human needs, social cohesion, equity and social justice, protection and optimum utilization of the environment as well as the empowerment of rural and vulnerable groups and communities (Nzeribe, 2017). A country is classified as developed, developing or underdeveloped based on the extent to which it is able to meet these criteria. It could be seen that these various definitions capture the multi-dimensional character of development, indicative of the fact that there is inherent potential for development in all human society.

Political Leadership

Political leadership, in a parsimonious definition, refers to the impact on decision-making and political outcomes that result from action by the holder of political office. Thus, it is connected with leadership style and may be rooted in certain character traits of the leader's

personality (Helms, 2012). He asserted that it is political leadership, which involves legislators, elected executives in the policy process such as presidents, governors, and mayors, and the various stakeholders in the political process.

Throughout history, leadership has been a factor of great significance in human cooperation. It has continued to exist in all human affairs. Many social scientists believe that no effective or successful group or community exists without leadership. Thus leadership is a ubiquitous historical phenomenon whenever and wherever human beings come together to form a group or community. Leadership, therefore, is an essential feature of all governments and governance. It is a truism that the success or failure of any government lies in the degree of its strengths and weaknesses. Leadership as a concept has been defined in various ways by many social scientists, each emphasizing one aspect of the concept or the other. However, we provide hereunder a few definitions of the concept “leadership”, which are of relevance to this paper.

Northhouse (2010) defines leadership as a process whereby an individual influences a group of individuals to achieve a common goal. For Ogbeidi (2012) leadership refers to that direct or indirect, planned or unplanned, conscious or unconscious group process, whereby an individual guides and influences the thoughts, feelings or behaviours of others for the purpose of achieving group goals and objectives. Thus a leader occupies a position of responsibility in coordinating the activities of members of the group in their task of attaining a common goal. From the foregoing, therefore, a leader is expected to demonstrate good character, vision, good sense of direction, prudence and above all ability to lead by good example because of the confidence the generality of the people impose on him.

Leadership and Governance in Nigeria

According to World Bank study of sub-Sahara Africa (SSA), the problem of Nigeria’s development is a crisis of governance; the study affirmed that because of the selfish interest of some state officials, who have served in one capacity or the other and have deliberately refused to give account of their activities while in office. Such office become personalized and politicized, thus paving ways for unnecessary patronage, which consequently undermine the authority of the leader. It thus becomes difficult for a sustainable and dynamic economy to grow in such environment (World Bank, 2014).

Basically, sixty three years independence is worth celebrating. But there is absolutely nothing to show for these sixty three years of existence. Nigeria of today cannot compete favourably with its counterpart in the march to development, especially in the areas of quality of life, infrastructural facilities, basic needs of life and technological development. This development problem was traced to inadequate and qualified personnel, lack of enough fund and low technology to drive the vehicle of development immediately after independence. But this is sixty three years after independence now, why is Nigeria still lagging behind? Should we still continue to hinge our underdevelopment on personnel and finance problem? Of course No, the major constraint to Nigeria’s development is lack of transformational leadership.

According to Onigbude (2017) “regrettably poor leadership performance has remained in with us despite years of complaints and grumbling. We have acquiesced in our own progressive destruction by submitting ourselves to the leadership of political misfits”. It is surprising that the so much expected dividends of democracy eluded the mass of the people, while the leadership has remained unaccountable to them.

According to Ugwu-Odo (2015), most of the problems Nigeria is facing today particularly, in term of development are caused by the sharp practices of our past and present leaders. In terms of accountability, transparency and service delivery, despite the abundance of human and natural resources that make the country the toast of many nations, our leaders have not been at their best as people's expectations of a better hope and opportunities have long be dashed, with governance ingredients still at its elusive stage to Nigerians. The leadership problem that has confronted Nigeria since independence is making the polity deteriorating. Few of the leaders if any, work for the development of the country more often than not, their policies are hastily put together and poorly executed. As a matter of fact, going by all the development parameters and performance indices, Nigerians leaders have failed, economically, macroeconomic stability, fiscal discipline, economic reforms, due process and relatively low inflation rates that the state could claim to have achieved sit alongside weak business confidence, low growth, massive unemployment, and rising inequality between the rich and the poor.

Nigeria's per capita GDP is nothing to reckon with, poverty is widespread and about 54 percent of the population is living on less than One US dollar Per Day. Nigeria ranks low on Human Development indices (HDI), ranked by the United Nations in 2007 as 157th out of 177 countries, down from 148th out of a total of 173 in 2003. The country's human development index of 0.453 in 2005 was lower than the average index for sub-Saharan Africa (0.515) and thereafter was rated as 13th least viable countries of the World. Every government has always promised to eradicate corruption at its inauguration which is continued unabated (Ayade, 2020). Perhaps the most profound definition of leadership thus far comes from Mudasiru (2015), who have stated that leadership is an influence process. They opined that leadership is the exercise of influence on the part of the leader over the behaviour of one or more persons. In other words, leadership involves one person trying to get others do something that he wants them to do. Agreeing with Mudasiru (2015) added the concept of goal attainment, when he contended that "leadership is the process of influencing the activities of an organized group towards goal setting and goal achievement".

This implies that a leader must be able to influence the followers towards setting appropriate goals and towards their effective achievement. In this regard, how much do Nigerian leaders influence their followers to set and achieve appropriate goals? Dawood (2019) defines leadership as the relationship through which one person influences the behaviour of other people. This explains that the process of leadership cannot be separated from the activities of groups. From the aforementioned this paper deduce that leadership is a process of influencing, directing and coordinating the activities of organized group towards goal setting, goal achievement and problem solving, that it necessarily involves taking initiative or initiating new structures and new procedures and that is imperatively a function of the leader and the situational variable.

Development according to Rodney (2009) is a phenomenon which is inherent in all societies. He further noted that development means growth or change or planned change. The term development has diverse perspectives such as social development, economic development, and political development. George-Genyi (2013) expressed that development is the process by which a type of (social) change is introduced into a system in order to produce a better production method and improved social arrangement. It involves a structural transformation of the economy, the society, the polity and the culture of a country. The level and rate of development of a particular society are influenced by so many variables such as the political culture, leadership style and corruption. Development in human society is not a one sided

process rather multisided issues; some scholars perceive development as an increase in the skill and ability. It is viewed as maximum freedom, and the ability to create responsibly. George-Genyi (2013), states that sustainable development does not involve capital accumulation and economic growth only but the condition in which people in a country have adequate food, job and income inequality. It is the process of bringing fundamental and sustainable changes in the society.

Political Intrigues as a Cover for Ineffective Political Leadership and Corruption in Nigeria

In a bid to stem the rising tide of opposition, political leaders, both civilian and military, exploit and manipulate the entrenched ethnic divide in Nigeria for political purposes. The forces of ethnic nationalism, therefore, have provided the platform for a refreshing opportunity to develop a more national agenda (Nosiri, 2019). Nigerian governments over the years lacked popular participation and consensus building. This has the effect of intensifying the exploitation of the hostile ethnic nature of the Nigerian state in the struggle to enforce legitimacy. Enforced legitimacy cannot, especially in an ethnically-differentiated society, stimulate national development. Rather, the polity continuously moves in a vicious circle of instability that proceeds in a ceaseless tide which threatens its existence.

Various tactics were employed for regime survival. This was worsened by a prolonged experience with dictatorial military rule. The common political intrigue associated with the civilian era was the propensity of the political elites to hang on to power through electoral malpractices, and, lately, orchestrated manipulation of the constitutional rules (Sklar, Onwudiwe & Kew, 2006). Intra and inter party squabbles, defection, threats of assassination and assassination among other political vices, leading to threats and counter threats of impeachment are employed to ensure the continuity of patron-client politics. Thus, meaningful developmental programmes were neglected, as efforts were concentrated on how to curtail the rising opposition forces.

The military leaders also exploited public opinion, by defusing inherent potential sources of opposition, suppressing and placating, employing reversal and insistence tactics in a bid to ensure a delicate balance of legitimacy. The period, (1985 - 1998) according to Nosiri (2019) witnessed several transition programmes like “trains without locomotion”, all to ensure an unstable political environment to facilitate self-perpetuation in power while corruption took the new dimension of becoming a national virtue rather than vice Thus:

Abacha's regime was even more terrible. Terror became a potent political weapon to legitimize his reign. While the government was implicated in the reign of terror that characterized the period, pro-democracy and human right activists were framed as the culprits (Albert, 2005). The series of bomb attacks during this period were a deliberate ploy to divert the attention of the people from the chronic government failures and subsequently curry the favour of both domestic and international actors for legitimacy (Albert, 2005).

The bomb attacks also became a veritable vehicle by which the government diverted the attention of the people from substantive issues in politics. Each blast was reported and discussed in the NTA and Radio Nigeria news for several weeks...all these were aimed at attracting sympathy for the government and through this kind of diversionary tactics Nigerians were led to forget about the fundamental issues in their nation's development while

‘sympathizing’ with the Head of state ‘whose genuine efforts towards lasting democracy’ were being thwarted by ‘subversive elements.’

The employment of political intrigues was facilitated by an inconsistent federal structure. The promise and implementation of state and local government creation exercises were employed as political weapon to induce beneficiaries to forget about the increased arbitrariness and political oppression, and encourage them to throw their support behind the government. In essence, the more the exercise to presumably create new states and local government areas, the less powerful and viable the component units of the federal structure, and the more the corruption networks in the system. National development suffers while personal enrichment increases. Thus, dysfunctional impediments to development were fueled by the use of political intrigues to disempower the civil society. Power consolidation through the manipulation of the fragile ethnic relationships made the overriding objectives of national development a failed project while a few individuals emerged as power brokers and “godfathers”. Unfortunately however, the civil society lacks the capacity to engage the government on the need to promote good governance through accountability and transparency.

Mudasiru (2015), has rightly observed, the dearth of basic resources, institutional capacity as well as professional skills in functional areas of expertise had weakened the ability of the various organizations to sustain the struggle and campaign against bad governmental policies. Consequently, neo-patrimonial power relationships flourished with its attendant undemocratic political culture. The “authoritarian hangover” of neopatrimonialism had stifled the political system of the essential virtues of accountability and effective representation.

The neopatrimonial power politics that pervaded the political landscape had subsequently entrenched clientelistic hierarchies among the political elites. This is a manifestation of the nature of politics in the society, which Nwanegbo and Odigbo (2015) sees as a negative phenomenon that should be altered. “The neopatrimonial contract between the ‘Big Man’ (usually a patron either in or outside the government) and his supporters is based on shared perspectives of how both see the relationship: in this hierarchical arrangement, legitimacy and power flow from the top down, and both patron and client presume that these privileges are inherent with power. The social position of the ‘Big Man’ is seen as the source that creates the relationship, such that the patronage flowing downward is a favor that demands loyalty in exchange.

The Impact of Leadership Crisis and Corruption on National Development

The impact of leadership crisis and corruption on national development in Nigeria will require voluminous narration and citations which the work of this nature does not permit. Therefore, a few issues have been identified as the drawbacks that leadership crisis and corruption in the public sector have affected. The impact of leadership crisis and corruption in the public sector on national development has resulted in the following:

- a) Poor infrastructural development which has brought about lack of power supply with its attendant negative consequences on industrial and economic development, substandard and crater-filled road networks which are more of a death trap than highways, poor quality and inadequate water supply and etc.;
- b) A decrepit health sector that merely provides medical and health consultation but refers serious health challenges to well-developed health systems in other countries thus triggering capital flight and boosting the health sector of other countries. As though it might sound, the late President Shehu Musa Y’aradua had no confidence in the Nigerian health system, which the ruling class he belonged to had created. Today,

- many government functionaries at the slightest health challenge scamper abroad to get the best medical treatment while leaving the generality of citizens to the mercy of the poorly funded and sparsely equipped health sector in the country;
- c) Falling standards in student and teacher education as a result of poor funding of education in the country. Nigerian graduates are becoming increasingly unemployable and may, sooner than later, lose the competitive edge for which products of the country's ivory towers were known for some years ago; as horrible as it sound, student sees education as a scam. Majority of graduated citizens have little or no job to fall on. Education is no more a yardstick for employment in the polity;
 - d) A morbid and porous security situation resulting in the wanton destruction of lives and property as currently initiated by the Boko Haram and herdsmen terror envoys and a cortege of criminal sociopaths such as armed robbers, carjackers, kidnappers, ritual killers and assassins and etc.;
 - e) A failed, insensitive or clueless political leadership which is fighting hard to appease their constituents with crumbs from the national cake while stealing large chunks for self-preservation and perpetuation.
 - f) Grinding and growing poverty almost slipping into an absolute status for over 90% of Nigerians who are caught in its vicious grips and are wondering how to escape their helpless situation;
 - g) An embryonic economy that is said to experience growth spurts without development. The spurt in the economy has not put food on many Nigerian's table, has failed to create jobs for the unemployed and has failed to improve the human development indices that make for genuine national development. The economic development in place has been plunged to the depths by the sustained thievery of public officials aided by their foreign allies and domestic private sector collaborators, fronts and cronies.

The multi-dimensional consequences of corrupt practices on a nation's socio-political and economic development cannot be overemphasized, as virtually all sectors of the country, including education, health, agriculture, politics, technology, etc., are negatively affected, with the resultant outcome like extreme poverty, high level of illiteracy, economic dependency, technological backwardness, political instability, etc., as the order of the day. Nigeria's situation typifies the above.

Leadership Crisis and Corrupt Acts in Nigeria

In tracing leadership crisis and corrupt acts in Nigeria, an analysis can be made of how leadership incapacity has led the country to its current state. Cases of corrupt acts undermined the First Republic headed by Sir Abubakar Tafawa Balewa and Dr. Nnamdi Azikwe, the Prime Minister and President respectively. This inadvertently provided the platform for a team of young middle-rank military officers to overthrow the leadership at different levels through the bloody coup d'état of 15th January 1966 (Ogbeidi, 2012).

The succeeding General Aguiyi Thomas Ironsi government constituted a number of commissions of inquiry to probe the conducts of some public institutions and to investigate corrupt acts that dogged public administration during the Balewa era. The findings of the commissions showed that some ministers established companies and abused their positions in securing contracts. Also, cases were proven in which the ministers misappropriated public funds while showing disdain towards established processes and procedures in the award of contracts by parastatals under their Ministries (Okonkwo, 2007).

The wrongdoers of the First Republic were eventually released by the government that came into power following the Gowon coup of July 1966. This resulted in negative consequences in which new leaders initiated largely misplaced and misguided projects, with the sole aim of siphoning public wealth. This scenario clearly showed that the military usurpers were not in any way better than the displaced civilian officials. General Yakubu Gowon was in power when Nigeria amassed unprecedented proceeds from the oil boom of the 1970s, with little to show in terms of probity and accountability. By 1974, cases of unmitigated levels of corrupt acts by Gowon's military administrators in charge of the states had dominated public discourse (Ogbeidi, 2012). By July 1975, the country witnessed another coup which brought in General Murtala Ramat Mohammed into power.

The 1975 coup made attempts at stemming the tide of corrupt acts in the public service. General Murtala Mohammed led the way by publicly declaring his assets and ordering all public officials to do same. The government constituted a number of panels to investigate former leaders. By 1975, the reports of the panels resulted in the dismissal of ten out of Gowon's twelve military governors following indictment by the Federal Assets Investigation Panel. The public officials also had assets in excess of the legitimate earnings confiscated (Maduagwu, quoted in Ogbeidi, 2012).

Commissions were also set up at the state level by the newly constituted governments which led to the sack of several public officials indicted of corrupt acts. As a matter of fact, a large percentage of the officials had to refund the ill-gotten wealth into public treasury. The fight against corruption was however cut short with the assassination of General Murtala six months into his tenure. His successor, General Olusegun Obasanjo, did little to maintain the zeal of his predecessor in the war on corrupt acts, until he handed over power to Shehu Shagari led democratically elected government in 1979. Corrupt acts subsequently reared its ugly head again under Shagari's administration of the Second Republic. The administration nested unmitigated levels of public sector corruption, with the leadership showing little interest in curbing the menace. This was also because access of funds was enhanced with reports that from 1979 to 1983 when Shagari oversaw governance in the country, oil proceeds amounting to more than US \$16 billion were pillaged (Ogbeidi, 2012).

General Muhammadu Buhari emerged to orchestrate a successful palace coup that displaced Shagari's overtly corrupt government on 31st December 1983. The regime undertook the war on corruption, indiscipline as well as public conformity with decent public life and conduct as its watchword. Like the Murtala regime, the government instituted investigative tribunals to probe civilian governors and heads of government ministries during the Shagari administration. The marginal gains recorded in the attack on corrupt behaviour were however flooded with human right abuses, thus heralding public applause when General Ibrahim Babangida led another place coup to ascend the presidential mantle in August 1985.

The Babangida regime would however go down in the historical books as one which gave very overt corrupt acts "an institutional structure" in Nigeria. The rate at which corrupt behaviour blossomed and festered under Babangida was so alarming to the point that indicted public officials of previous regimes led by Murtala and Shagari emerged to retake their confiscated possessions. They also returned strategic positions in public life. The situation is well highlighted by Maduagwu thus:

Not only did the regime encourage corruption by pardoning corrupt officials convicted by his predecessors and returning their seized properties, the regime officially sanctioned corruption in the country and

made it difficult to apply the only potent measures, long prison terms and seizure of ill-gotten wealth, for fighting corruption in Nigeria in the future (Ogbeidi, 2012).

The Babangida regime was halted following heightened public disapproval of his continued stay in office. He constituted and handed over power to an Interim National Government headed by Chief Earnest Shonekan in August 1993. The Interim National Government was subsequently displaced by Babangida's Chief of Army Staff, General Sani Abacha in November 1993. Abacha then adopted and vastly consolidated on the corrupt acts of the Babangida years. While General Abacha held power, corruption became completely entrenched in public sector ethos in Nigeria. Abacha, his family, friends and associates committed a level of looting never before witnessed in the country's history, with Transparency International in its Global Corruption Report of 2004 rating the regime as the fourth most corrupt in human history, embezzling public funds to the tune of US\$ 5 billion. Abacha's continued onslaught on public wealth came to a sudden end when he died in office on 8th June, 1998. His successor, General Abdulsalami Abubakar, quickly set out to redeem the battered image of both the military institution and the Nigerian nation by handing over power to an elected civilian administration in May 1999, heralding the Fourth Republic (Ogbeidi, 2012).

The Olusegun Obasanjo administration which emerged at the dawn of the Fourth Republic in 1999 put mechanisms, structures and institutions in place to combat public and private sector graft in Nigeria. The government instituted reforms, consolidated on the country's anti-corruption laws and instituted the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) to combat corrupt acts in both the public and private sectors. This has not however stemmed the tide of corruption in the country. A critical appraisal of the synopsis of political leaders and corrupt acts in Nigeria will buttress a clear cut relationship, with successive public official's attaining power, guarded with the intention of amassing stupendous wealth at the expense of public good and worthy service.

Theoretical Framework

This is anchored on Modernization or linear theory of development. This is an attempt by Euro-American scholars to explain Third World underdevelopment as a consequence of Third World countries inability to attain the industrial and technological levels of modernity found in Europe and America (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2022). Using the "index-gap approach", modernization theory assumes that disparities or gaps exist between the industrialized countries of Euro-America and the poor colonized countries of the Third World (Robert, 2009). Diffusions, a subset of the Modernization theory poses the question- How are these gaps to be filled? - By diffusing modernizing elements from developed to underdeveloped countries like Nigeria. What then are these modernizing elements that ought to be diffused into underdeveloped countries? These include: foreign finance capital, foreign technology, (this explains the policy of transfer of technology), foreign educational, religious, political institutions including the mass media, foreign values, as well as foreign philosophies and ideologies. These are supposedly modernizing catalysts which will enable underdeveloped countries to develop.

The Psychological/Psychodynamic approach, of the modernization theory, recommends that to ensure a high degree of assimilation of these diffused elements into the socio-culture and production organs of Third World countries, there should be a change in the socio-culture and

personality features of these underdeveloped countries. This is why the middle class was created where it was non-existent. Members of this class are usually sponsored and consolidated wherever they exist, because they are assumed to foster modernization more than other classes. The modernization theory sees development as given by Euro-American.

Thus, by implication, Third World countries such as Nigeria can only develop by adopting policies and practices which will enable them to recreate themselves in the image of the developed countries. What this also means is that all countries of the world should move along the same linear path of development irrespective of their different historical colonial experiences and worldviews. Critics however, believe that the more Third World countries adopt and implement these modernizing prescriptions from their western Atlantic mentors, the more dependent, they have become. The un-tenability of its assumptions as well as its insinuations forced the modernization theory into an early retreat.

Conclusion

It is obvious from the above analysis that poor leadership and corruption are related factors that have done a damaging effect on Nigeria's economy, hence the inability of Nigeria to develop to take its rightful position in the world. The situation could be worse with the fallen oil prices, the depreciation of the Naira, and the depleting of Nigeria's foreign reserves. Political leadership in Nigeria is about self-service not service to the people. It is clear that corruption is a cankerworm that has eaten into the fabric of the Nigerian economy. Since it has entered the system, Nigeria's administrative and social lexicon regressed unto an era of ethical breakdown. It is found that although corruption is a universal phenomenon, its magnitude and effects are more severe and deep-seated in Nigeria.

This paper equally found that all forms of corruption manifested in bribery, frauds, embezzlement, election rigging, examination malpractice, etc., are noticeable in Nigeria. From the review of related literature, it was also discovered that corruption has caused decay and dereliction within the infrastructure of government and the society in physical, social and human terms. It is opined that corruption has been responsible for the instability of successive governments, since the First Republic and it has contributed immensely to unbridle looting most especially in public offices. Again, this has virtually turned Nigeria into the land of starvation and a debtor nation in spite of the nation's enormous resources. It shows that corruption is literally the anti-thesis of development and progress in Nigerians political leadership.

The paper has argued that of all the deepening crises of militating against Nigeria's quest for socio-political and economic development, the most daunting appear to be ineffective political leadership, untamed and seemingly untamable corruption and bad governance. The central opinion of this paper is that corruption has been completely institutionalized into the contemporary Nigerian economic and socio-political systems and this is now reflecting in the growth and development of the nation. This paper discovered that all forms of corruption manifested in bribery, frauds, embezzlement, election rigging, examination malpractice and etc. are noticeable in Nigeria. The conclusion however, is that no matter the magnitude of natural resources present, the size of the foreign exchange earnings, technological know-how, the efficiency of labour and the availability of basic infrastructure, development cannot be sustained in Nigeria except corruption is eradicated. More so, no matter the magnitude of natural resources present, the size of the foreign exchange earnings, technological know-how, the efficiency of labour and the availability of basic infrastructure, development cannot be sustained in Nigeria except corruption is eradicated.

Recommendations

The study recommended the following:

- 1) the citizens should play their own role in seeing that they perform their civic duties efficiently by electing those that are credible not out of religious or ethnic affiliations, the leader must be a patriotic one, willing to deliver and self-denial;
- 2) there should be a strong anti-graft law which must be independent from either the judiciary, executive and the legislature, any administration that must lead must come in through a credible free and fair elections;
- 3) a reform should be created and targeted towards stimulating economic growth, reduce unemployment, reduce poverty, improve government accountability and transparency, re-orienting values and rebuilding national integrity.

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